

Papal Seminary Bids Adieu to Kuru

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It is said that some people come into our lives and leave footprints on our hearts and we are never ever the same. It is indeed true with Kuru.

I should say this at the outset, Kuru is one of the main influences for my coming to Papal Seminary and for making me feel at home. Though we are from the same province we rarely met each other in the province except as scholastics during summer vacations.

Kuru is originally from Kerala and belongs to Dumka-Raiganj Jesuit province of the Society of Jesus. He has completed his B.sc Physics from Loyola College, Chennai and M. SC Physics from Trichy St. Joseph's; he has Masters in Philosophy and Theology from JD and 2 doctorates (theology & Philosophy) from Innsbruck. Kuru has written more than 30 books and countless articles. He was the Dean of the Faculty of Philosophy, JD, Pune for more than six years.

Kuru was always available for any work in Papal Seminary. He was deeply committed to Papal seminary for the last 27 years. He does not bother about his dress code and style. We can find him at times with the pants zip open, shirt or T-shirt inside out, two different types of slippers at the same time, and torn shoes at international conferences (in S. Korea where I was present). Forgetfulness is another great quality of Kuru. But he has a tremendous capacity for hard work. When he was a student of philosophy and theology, he was a teacher to many students (sisters and brothers). Many would flock around him. After a good party, we can see Kuru going straight to bed fully dressed, otherwise he may be naked, but he is up for work at the computer at 3.00 in the morning and sending emails. He has a record with details of most of the staff members who have gone away from here for the last several years. There are many more things to narrate; if I narrate all of them, the whole day will not be enough.

He becomes very upset and angry when we refuse great and important responsibilities. I showed no interest in applying to get the title, Professor. It was mainly because Kuru assured me that I applied for the post of professorship. Before that, I had to publish my doctorate thesis for which Kuru very generously helped me. He checked my thesis so that I could publish it. He was instrumental in finding the publisher. Kuru is always a pleasant and affectionate character. He is such a gentle character that people easily like him, and he does not know how to offend people; very approachable to students and staff. Many students could get the secular Bachelor's degree during his time as Dean. He went out of his way to help them.

I had guessed that it would be hard to say goodbye and I was right - it is hard. Yet not only I but most of us consider ourselves fortunate to have met such a special, multi-talented, a very intelligent, and simple person, a person like Kuru. Therefore, saying goodbye to him is hard!

As we say farewell, we remind ourselves that farewells are not forever, nor are they the end. They are simply words to say that we will miss you dearly and that we will remember you fondly. Although we may be separated by irregular visits, nothing will diminish the important roles that you have and always will play in our lives. We are going to miss you deeply, for the liveliness you brought whenever you were around, for the spark your enthusiasm could ignite, the infinite variety that you possess and for the sheer dedication you gave your job. Replacing you is going to be very difficult. On behalf of the whole community, I wish you happy adventures and challenges in XLRI, fantastic new

friendships, amazing experiences, and hope to see you shining brighter and achieve what you truly deserve. We shall remain physically and emotionally very close to you. I shall conclude this with the famous blessing: May the road rise up to meet you, may the wind be ever at your back. May the sun shine warm upon your face and the rain fall softly on your fields. And until we meet again, may God hold you in the hollow of his hand.

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